

EMPLOYEE RETENTION THAT AFFECTS THE PERFORMANCE OF PRIVATE HOSPITAL EMPLOYEES

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Abstract

The objective of this research was to investigate employee retention factors that affect the performance of private hospital employees. The study sample consisted of 400 hospital employees in Bangkok. The tool used to store data is questionnaires. The statistics used in the data analysis include percentage, average, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, Pearson's simple correlation coefficient, and stepwise multiple regression analysis statistics. The statistical significance is defined at the level of 0.05. The results showed that 400 employees, mostly female, under 25 years old, mostly married status, bachelor's degree, 1–5 years of service, employee retention factors. Overall, it is at the highest level, and if considered individually, it is found that the first factor is the working environment. Secondary, Relationships with people in the workplace and Career Path. Finally, Job security. Overall employee productivity is at the highest level. And if considered individually, it is found that the first priority is Speed of operation, followed by Quality of work, and the last order is Personal skills. In the stepwise multiple regression analysis, it was found that the performance of employees correlated with the working environment (X_1) and Relationships with people in the workplace (X_2) and Job security (X_3) and Career Path (X_4) Or it can be described as a regression relationship equation. As follows: Efficiency of private hospital employees = $.771 + (.290 * X_1) + (.290 * X_2) + (.215 * X_3) + (.201 * X_4)$.

Keywords: Maintenance / Performance / Private Hospital Staff

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, business organizations have undergone significant changes, especially changes in the limited workforce rate, work restructuring, quality assurance, and the impact of the economic downturn. This results in less welfare and rewards. This problem, if not corrected properly, will cause personnel operations to not be as efficient as desired, causing various problems as a result. All problems, no matter how difficult, can be solved with human resources who have the potential, readiness to perform tasks successfully for themselves and the organization. Therefore, modern organizations that are ready must focus on developing departments and human resources at the same time. By setting the goals of the unit for increased performance as well as the feelings of the workers to achieve job satisfaction, to be able to create real success in the job. Elements of management of various organizations, whether public, private or state enterprises. The most important factor for operation is people, if any organization can manage human resources to work for maximum benefit, it will create progress for the organization. Mental demand, encouragement, and

satisfaction are key to enhancing job efficiency. Job satisfaction, attitude or feelings of a person towards the work performed when the work is fulfilling both materially and psychologically, thus creating a need to perform the job and willing to devote time, physical effort, thought, to meet the needs of the agency. Employee retention is particularly valuable, resulting in an increasing number of talented and skilled personnel in the organization, reducing attendance, eliminating the burden of teaching new employees. A stable team is formed, with love, bonding and mutual understanding. Highly skilled employees can help reduce job duties for supervisors more than employees who are in the process of learning the job, so there are no problems on the job or very few problems because employees are more skilled than new employees. The organization will develop continuously because there are employees who know the job as skilled and able to take initiative in new jobs (Bangmo, S., 2015).

Therefore, work efficiency is due to the satisfaction of the personnel in the organization as well. This affects the success of the job and the organization, as well as the happiness of the workers. In other words, if any organization has no personal satisfaction with their work, it may be one of the reasons for inefficient performance and performance, resulting in a decrease in the quality of work and a negative effect on the organization, causing damage to the work and causing discipline problems as well. But on the other hand, if the organization has satisfied personnel at work, it will positively affect its performance. It is also a reflection of the efficiency of operations and leadership of the executives of that organization if any organization sees the importance of work efficiency to the personnel in its unit and understands the factors or elements that affect the efficiency. They are also aware that their enthusiasm for work can change at any time, according to circumstances or time (Wonganutaroj, P., 2012).

The public health system, especially in private healthcare facilities, has changed dramatically. In terms of improving the quality of administration and services, healthcare organizations must be aware and alert in order to improve the quality of administration and services in line with changes in society. This change must be in line with the changing environment, competition by the organization in the future will focus on diversity, learning, continuous improvement. If one wishes to improve the quality of nursing services, one important thing to study is the quality of life of the personnel involved. Continuous improvement of quality of life at work is one of the ways to develop the organization that will affect the people working in the organization to work happily and efficiently, as well as to maintain employees to work continuously for the hospital (Wannai, V., 2015: 1-3) Therefore, executives should pay attention to the thoughts and minds of people who work and give importance to people by treating people as one of the valuable assets of the organization. Quality of work as an element or dimension of quality of life is of great importance to work today. The quality of life of personnel is of great importance in every organization because it shows the relationship with job satisfaction or motivation in various areas of work, as well as affects the retention of good employees. This affects the quality of working life in terms of progress, knowledge and capability development, efficient work performance, and continuous performance of the organization (Chalermnan, P., 2013).

From the above, the researcher is interested in studying "Employee retention that affects the performance of private hospital employees" by applying concepts and theories as a guide to study employee retention factors that affect the performance of private hospital employees, whether in terms of working volume to meet targets, time spent on operations, and other matters. This will lead to planning guidelines to increase the effectiveness of personnel operations.

Research Objectives

1. To study employee retention factors that affect the performance of private hospital employees.
2. To study the relationship of employee retention to the performance of private hospital employees.

Research Hypothesis

Employee retention factors affect the performance of private hospital employees.

Concept Related Theories

Boonrit, N. (2015) states that performance refers to the achievement of desirable or expected objectives or goals. It is based on the comparison of the results of the project work or activities received with the objectives or goals.

Fupleum, S. (2015) states that preservation refers to negative attitudes and beliefs about work that lead to negative feelings towards work. This affects the expression of behaviors such as absence, being late, being inefficient, as well as quitting a job. Therefore, establishing a positive attitude towards sales work is extremely important to keep employees with the organization, because attitude is what determines a person's way of thinking that affects actions. If the salesperson has a positive attitude towards sales, the salesperson will fully commit to work and the organization.

Herberg's two-factor theory (1959, cited in Patimetheeporn, D., 2013) states that factors that affect job satisfaction are factors that enhance motivation for employees to have higher work efficiency and higher job satisfaction, divided into two groups: motivational factor and maintenance or hygiene factor.

Conceptual framework for research

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

The population used in this research was 73,766 full-time employees of 105 private hospitals in Bangkok (National Statistical Office, 2017: 11-22). These include personnel in 3 groups as follows: medical staff, medical service personnel, and hospital service personnel. The researcher calculated the sample size with Taro Yamane's formula (1970). A tolerance of 0.05 equals 400 people. In Stage 1, researcher determined the sampling according to the temperature and the number of private hospitals in Bangkok totaling 105 hospitals, with 4 respondents per hospital, totaling 420 questionnaires. After that, in step 2, a random quota method for collecting data was determined to determine the respondents who would be represented in each private hospital in Bangkok. The researcher used a non-return lottery sampling method to determine the respondents from the selected sample, and when the questionnaire was returned, researcher selected 400 complete questionnaires to match the specified sample.

Research Instruments

Research instruments are questionnaires created by researchers based on the study of concepts and theories from relevant research for use in the study. By division the inquiry is divided into 4 parts as follows: Part 1 about general information of the sample group, namely gender, age, status, education level, duration of work, 15 items. Part 2 About Employee Retention Factors, 19 items and Part 3 is about employee productivity, 15 items. The question Part 2 and Part 3 are Likert's scale questionnaires with 5 levels: highest, High, moderate, low and lowest. And Part 4 Suggestions.

Steps to create a tool

The researcher have established the process of creating a tool for research studies by studying data from documents and research related to employee retention factors that affect the performance of private hospital employees, to apply theories and concepts as a guideline for questionnaire creation, create a questionnaire that covers the content to be studied, and then submit the generated questionnaire to three experts for review to determine the content validity and improve the questionnaire according to expert feedback. The questionnaire was then tried out with a group similar to the sample of 30 subjects and analyzed for reliability by finding Crorbach's Alpha Coefficient and double-check and complete the correct before using it for further data collection.

Instrument Quality Inspection

The researcher used questionnaires created for research studies to test for precision. (Validity) and Reliability

1. Finding precision by using questionnaires created by the researcher to verify the accuracy of the content from 3 experts. After that, find the Conformity Index (IOC) value by selecting questions with an IOC value greater than 0.6 as the question. The questionnaire used in the study showed an average of not less than 0.6.
2. To determine confidence, we took the updated questionnaire to a try-out with a group of 30 people who were similar to the study population. By finding Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient, the confidence of the questionnaire was 0.911, which indicates that the question is reliable.

Collection of Information

The researcher used a questionnaire to collect data from 400 people. The researcher has the following steps:

1. The researcher coordinated with the hospital to request permission to collect the data.
2. The researcher gave the sample, a questionnaire and explained the topic.
3. Once the respondents have successfully completed the questionnaire, the researcher checks the completeness of the questionnaire answers.
4. The questionnaire received is re-coded for evaluation using statistical packages.

Analysis of data and statistics used

1. Description Statistics describe a sample of qualitative variables using frequency and percentage statistics. Quantitative variables use Maximum, Minimum, Mean, and Standard Deviation. Performance analysis of private hospital employees using mean and standard deviation.

Interpretation of means: Analysis is performed by finding the mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (Tirakanand, S., 2013: 183-191). According to the evaluation criteria along the lines of Best W. John. (1997: 190) as follows:

An average of 4.50-5.00 indicates the highest feedback level.

An average of 3.50-4.49 means a high feedback level.

An average of 2.50-3.49 indicates a moderate feedback level.

An average of 1.50-2.49 indicates a low feedback level.

An average of 1.00-1.49 indicates the lowest feedback level.

2. Inferential statistical analysis is used to test hypotheses as follows:

- 2.1 Checking the correlation between all independent variables based on the criteria laid down in the preliminary agreement of Linear Regression Analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient's simple correlation coefficient to find the relationship between quantitative variables.
- 2.2 Examine the appropriateness of models of employee retention factors that affect the performance of private hospital employees. VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) is not less than 5, Tolerance is not less than 0.2, and Eigen Value is not more than 1.0, so that all independent variables have no correlation and do not form a multicollinearity relationship.
- 2.3 Analysis of employee retention models that affect the performance of private hospital employees Stepwise Multiple Regression Analysis
- 2.4 Create employee retention models that affect the performance of private hospital employees.

FINDINGS

General information of 400 private hospital employees, mostly female, under 25 years old, marital status, bachelor's degree, and working period of 1-5 years as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: General information of the sample

General information of the sample	Amount (n= 400)	Percent
Gender		
Male	177	44.25
Female	223	55.75
Age		
Under 25 years old	122	30.50
25-30 years	109	27.25
31-35 years	95	23.75
From 36 years old	74	18.50
Status		
Single	189	47.25
Married	194	48.50
Widowed / Divorced / Separated	17	4.25
Education Level		
Undergraduate	97	24.25
Bachelor's degree	213	53.25
Postgraduate	90	22.50
Duration of Work		
Less than 1 year	54	13.50
1 – 5 years	230	57.50
6 – 10 years	75	18.75
More than 11 years	41	10.25

The results of the analysis of employee retention factors and the overall picture are at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.27, S.D.=.347). And if considered on a case-by-case basis, Working Environment is at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.35, S.D.=.465), Relationships with people in the workplace were at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.27, S.D.=.417). And the Career Path is at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.26, S.D.=.405). Finally, Job security is at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.22, S.D.=.483), According to Table 2

Table 2: Average and standard deviation, employee retention factors, and overview

Employee Retention Factors	Comment Level		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	Interpret the results
1. Working Environment	4.35	.465	highest
2. Relationships with people in the workplace	4.27	.417	highest
3. Career Path	4.26	.405	highest
4. Job Security	4.23	.483	highest
Overview	4.29	.334	highest

Analysis of employee performance, aspects and overview It was found that overall, it was at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.29, S.D.=.334). And if considered individually, the speed of operation is at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.32, S.D.=.440) and the quality of work is at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.32, S.D.=.413). Finally, personal skills are at the highest level (\bar{x} = 4.24, S.D.=.376), According to Table 3

Table 3: Average and standard deviation of employee performance and overview

Employee Productivity	Comment Level		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	Interpret the results
1. Speed of operation	4.32	.440	highest
2. Personal skills	4.24	.376	highest
3. Quality of work	4.32	.413	highest
Overview	4.29	.334	highest

The results of the correlation analysis between employee retention factors affecting the performance of private hospital employees were correlated with no more than .80, making all independent variables. Working Environment, Relationships with people in the workplace, Career Path and Job security. For the model, the factor influencing the performance of private hospital employees is the performance of private hospital employees = $.771 + (.290 * X_1) + (.290 * X_2) + (.215 * X_3) + (.201 * X_4)$. The correlation coefficient between employee retention factors affecting the performance of private hospital employees and the standard error in forecasting is $\pm .163$, as shown in Tables 4 and 5 as follows:

Table 4: Correlation coefficient between employee retention factors affecting the performance of private hospital employees

Factors	Z	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄
1. Z	1.000				
2. X ₁	.758**	1.000			
3. X ₂	.619**	.391**	1.000		
4. X ₃	.706**	.602**	.404**	1.000	
5. X ₄	.627**	.525**	.531**	.451**	1.000

** Statistically significant at the level of 0.05

Substitute for:

- Z represents Employee Productivity
- X₁ represents Working Environment
- X₂ represents Relationships with people in the workplace
- X₃ represents Job Security
- X₄ represents Career Path

Table 5: Analysis of appropriate models of performance of private hospital employees

Performance	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Constant	1.926	1.091	.906	.771
Working Environment (X ₁)	.545	.438	.322	.290
Relationships with people in the workplace (X ₂)		.305	.256	.215
Job security (X ₃)			.213	.201
Career Path (X ₄)				.116
R ²	.575	.697	.754	.766
S.E.	.218	.185	.167	.163
F	277.161**	82.658**	47.050**	10.073**
p-value of F	.000	.000	.000	.002

** It has statistical significance at the level of 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Based on the findings of this research, the researcher has brought the key points to discuss the results as follows:

Employee Retention is at the highest level overall, and if considered as the first priority, Working Environment, as it is important to help employees work more efficiently. Relationships with people in the workplace because building relationships with colleagues will result in more effective collaborative work, and the Career Path because it is a goal that every employee wants and motivates employees to work better and more efficiently. Finally, Job security because when employees are stable, it will make employees work more fully and efficiently. It has been demonstrated that employee retention factors, motivate and motivate employees to work better, more efficiently for their individual goals. In line with Herzberg's theory (1959, cited in Patimetheeporn, D., 2013) mentions the theory of two factors affecting job satisfaction is that it reinforces the motivation for employees to have higher work efficiency and higher job satisfaction, divided into 2 groups: motivational factor and maintenance or hygiene factor.

Performance: The overall performance of employees is at the highest level. First, the speed of operation, because the sooner the work is done, the more it affects the profit and income of the organization and quality. In order for the organization to develop its work, it must be efficient and accurate. Finally, personal skills because individual personal skills are what increases the efficiency of the job, the more skills that match their department, the more effective the work will be. It shows that employee productivity is what helps to improve the organization. In line with Aksiriwittaya, C. (2016), concept of performance namely: (1) the characteristics of the organization, which has 2 indicators: the structure of the organization can be determined by decentralization, division of labor according to specialization, formality (2) The nature of the environment, which is determined by 2 aspects of the environment, namely the internal and external environment (3) Characteristics of employees, based on commitment to the organization and performance (4) Management and implementation policy is the setting of certain goals, the provision and use of resources, the creation of an operational environment, processes, communication, leadership and decision-making, organizational adaptation, and new initiatives. In line with the research of Janmuangthai, W., Rodjam, C., Sriviboon, C. and Sitthiwarongchai, C. (2021: 60), it states that good performance is the result of good

management, which will guide the development of the capabilities of officers, personnel to be ready, knowledgeable, competent and good attitude to perform their duties.

Hypothetical Test Results Model of employee retention factors affecting the performance of employees of private hospitals in Bangkok It was found that the Career Path came in for further analysis and had the power to explain. Performance increased to 76.6 percent, with a standard error in forecasting of .163. It was found that Working Environment, Relationships with people in the workplace and Job security was statistically significantly correlated with performance at the level of 0.05. And later, when the progression variables were analyzed together, the level was 0.05 as well. This means that Working Environment, Relationships with people in the workplace, Job security and Progress affect the productivity of employees of private hospitals in Bangkok. It can be written as a regression equation in the form of a standard score as follows: Private Hospital Employee Performance = .771 + (.290 * x₁) + (.290 * x₂) + (.215 * x₃) + (.201 * x₄) In line with Herzberg's theory, (1959 cited in Patimetheeporn, D., 2013) states that the factors affecting job satisfaction are factors that enhance motivation for employees to have higher work efficiency and higher job satisfaction, divided into two groups: motivational factor and maintenance or hygiene factor. This is in line with the concepts of Aksiriwittaya, C. (2016) and Tanthikul. J. and Sittiworongchai, C. (2017: 54-66) on performance including Speed of operation, Personal skills and Quality of work.

Suggestion

1. Recommendations derived from the implementation of research findings
 - 1.1 According to the research, the working environment affects the performance of employees of private hospitals to a large extent, so the working environment should be given great importance to the best performance.
 - 1.2 Organizations should focus on and promote the performance of private hospital employees in terms of speed of work, quality of work, and skills of individuals. By taking into account the appropriateness of the competence of each employee, department or individual in order to increase the efficiency of employees.
2. Suggestions for next research
 - 2.1 This research is only exploratory research. By using a query as a tool. Therefore, in future studies, qualitative research methodologies such as interviews should be used to obtain additional insights, to be included in the study.
 - 2.2 In the next research, other areas should be studied further for improvement and development. Employee retention factors that influence the performance of private hospital employees in other aspects than those studied in this study, such as work motivation factors or welfare factors, etc., to cover factors that affect employee retention and performance of private hospital employees, as stated.

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